

Overcapacity in European power systems: analysis and robust optimization approach*

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Abstract

The planning of national power systems is traditionally based on long-term forecasts of electricity demand and fuel prices. However, over such long time horizons (20-50 years), these forecasts often prove to be inaccurate. As an example, wrong projections of low natural gas prices and high electricity demand in Europe in the early 2000s stimulated massive investments in electricity generation, which led to the current situation of overcapacity in the European electricity market. In this work, we first present the issue of overcapacity in Europe and discuss its causes; in particular, we highlight the relationship between overcapacity and errors in forecasts of electricity demand and fuel prices. Then, we apply a novel robust optimization framework to a real-world strategic energy planning problem, and compare it to the standard, deterministic decision-making approach. The results show that the robust investment strategies are up to 58% less likely to require future modifications leading to overcapacity. Overall, this suggests that considering uncertainties in the long-term planning process can reduce the risk of generating overcapacity in national power systems.

Keywords: Strategic energy planning; Power systems; Electricity generation; Uncertainty; Overcapacity; Robust optimization

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1 Introduction

Electrification - i.e. expanding the use of electricity in the heating (e.g. via heat pumps) and transportation (e.g. via electric mobility) sectors - together with the transition to a more renewable electricity mix, is a fundamental driver for the decarbonization of energy systems [1]. In other words, the energy transition [2] of a country is interlinked with the long-term planning of its electric power generation sector. Depending on the circumstances, a national electricity sector can be characterized by *undercapacity* or *overcapacity*. Our contribution with the present paper is twofold: we first discuss in the Introduction these two cases and analyze the current situation of overcapacity in Europe; then, we apply the novel robust optimization (RO) framework we proposed in [3] to a real-world case study, and show that overcapacity could be prevented by considering uncertainties in the strategic planning phase.

1.1 Undercapacity and the risk of power shortages

Undercapacity is the case in which the installed electric power generation capacity is undersized, i.e. not sufficient to satisfy the electricity demand. Systemic undercapacity is still a major issue in developing countries, where financial difficulties often limit investments and thus generate high level of unserved demand, as discussed by Afful-Dadzie et al. [4] for the case of Ghana.

In developed countries, undercapacity issues are generally limited to isolated events, known as *blackouts*. In particular, in the early 2000s two main electricity crises took place in California [5] and in Italy [6], respectively. As the early 2000s were also the years in which US and European electricity markets were transitioning towards more deregulated schemes, this led various authors to the conclusion that free electricity markets could be a barrier to new investments and, as a consequence, could generate undercapacity problems. As an example, in 2002 de Vries and Hakvoort [7] commented that “*in theory, liberalised electricity markets appear to be able to provide the optimal amount of generation capacity. [...] In real markets, a number of factors exist which may increase the investment risk and, therefore, the probability of capacity shortages*”; two years later Wen et al. [5] added that “*investment on new generation capacity additions is a commercial and risky activity and is expected to become more prudent under the deregulated electricity market environment.*”.

Among the different solutions proposed in the early 2000s to limit the risk of power shortages, *capacity payment* policies met a broad consensus. In general, capacity mechanisms can be defined as measures taken by a state designed to support investment to fill an expected capacity gap and ensure security of supply [8]; Bunn and Larsen [9] define capacity payments as the expected cost of unserved energy. In other words, the basic idea of capacity payment schemes is to compensate generators not only for the electricity they produce, but also for offering a given amount of installed backup capacity, thus favoring investments in new capacity which investors would otherwise be probably unwilling to make. Enforcement of capacity payment policies has been advocated by Fraser and Lo Passo [6] for the case of Italy after the 2003 blackout, and more generally by various other authors (such as Wen et al. [5] and Hach and Spinler [10]), some of them proposing as well novel capacity payment mechanisms [11].

1.2 Overcapacity in Europe: why it can be a problem and what are its main causes

Overall, the different capacity mechanisms adopted in Europe in the early 2000s to limit the risk of power shortages [8] led to massive investments in power generation, mostly of natural gas (NG) combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) power plants [12]. If, on the one hand, this successfully prevented from the risk of blackouts, on the other hand it ended up generating a

Table 1: Installed electricity generation capacity at the end of 2015 and yearly peak electricity demand in the same year. Data provided by the ENTSO-E, <https://www.entsoe.eu>.

	Installed capacity [GW _e]			Peak demand [GW _e]
	Fossil	Renewable ^a	Total ^b	
Germany	78.7	89.3	188.5	77.5
Italy	69.7	32.3	124.2	59.6
Portugal	6.5	5.9	18.5	8.6
Spain	47.0	30.7	106.2	40.3
The Netherlands	25.6	5.5	32.2	17.8

^aExcluding hydro

^bIncluding fossil, renewable, hydroelectric and nuclear capacity.

large overcapacity¹ in the European electricity market.

This overcapacity is shown in Figure 1, comparing the investments made in new capacity against peak electricity demand for four European countries (Italy, Spain, Portugal, The Netherlands) in the years 2000-2015. The figure illustrates that while installed capacity sharply increased over this period of time, demand remained stable compared to the year 2000. The lower part of Figure 1 additionally shows that the new installed capacity was rather evenly shared between fossil and renewable plants.

Table 1 shows the installed capacity and the yearly peak loads for the same countries in the year 2015: in all countries the total installed capacity is about twice the annual peak electricity demand, reaching a factor 2.6 for the case of Spain. The table includes as well the data for Germany, where in the years 2000-2015 the installed capacity increased by 74.5 GW_e; the country’s annual electricity consumption, instead, was higher in the year 2000 than in 2015.

As previously mentioned, most of the new investments were made on NG CCGT power plants. This situation of overcapacity in Europe has strongly impacted the profitability of these new power plants in the recent years [13]. As an extreme example, in the Netherlands newly constructed CCGT power plants were shut down in 2014 because non economically viable to operate [14]. In the case of Spain, Ciarreta et al. [15] found that after the massive entry of renewable energy sources in the electricity market, CCGT was the technology that suffered the most drastic reduction, both in production and in operating hours, the latter dropping from 5119 h/y in 2005 to 1000 h/y in 2013. As Hach and Spinler [10] conclude, “*gas-fired power generation is becoming increasingly unprofitable and hence undesirable for investors. This applies to existing plants as well as to new projects. [...] Gas-fired power plants were unprofitable most of 2012 in France, the Netherlands, Spain, the Czech Republic, and Germany.*”

Overcapacity in the electricity sector is also an endemic problem in the UK [16] and in China [17]. For China, Yuan et al. [18] estimate an excess coal capacity of 200 GW_e for the year 2020, mainly due to low growth of electricity demand; similarly, Ming et al. [19], studying the situation of the thermal overcapacity in the country, highlight that by the end of the year 2015, China’s thermal power installed capacity reached up to 990 GW_e, with an annual growth of 7.8%, which is much higher than the growth-speed of electric power demand (0.5%).

Why can overcapacity be a problem? As previously discussed, having an excess capacity in a power system can indeed be an advantage with respect to energy security and prevention

¹Overcapacity is the case in which the installed electric power generation capacity is oversized, i.e. in excess compared to the electricity demand.

Figure 1: a) Total new installed electricity generation capacity vs. yearly peak electricity demand and b) new fossil vs. new renewable capacity in Italy, Spain, Portugal, the Netherlands (years 2000-2015, year 2000 = 0). Data provided from ENTSO-E (<https://www.entsoe.eu>), except for 2000-2005 peak demand: Italy data from Terna (<http://www.terna.it>); Spain data from REE (<http://www.ree.es>); Portugal data from REN (sent via email, March 2018); Netherlands data extrapolated based on annual electricity consumption.

of power shortages. However, the experience of the last decade has shown that overcapacity can also constitute an issue. This is due to three main reasons. *i*) First, if capacity payment policies are adopted, as it is the case in various European countries, overcapacity becomes a cost for the public. As an example of this, Hawker et al. [8] cite the case of Portugal, where the capacity market was abolished in 2013 following concerns about overcapacity, as the additional cost placed on consumers was not seen as justifiable for the level of security gained. Similarly, del Río and Janeiro [12] comment that overcapacity results in a suboptimal allocation of economic resources. *ii*) Second, as highlighted by Banfi et al. [20], Genoese et al. [21] and Ciarreta et al. [15], overcapacity tends to lower the market price of electricity, which in turn limits new investments and thus *iii*) delays the low-carbon energy transition [12].

del Río and Janeiro [12] analyze the main causes leading to overcapacity situations in national power generation systems. Besides the fear of power shortages and the lack of appropriate coordination of government policies (e.g. between renewable deployment incentives and developments in the conventional generation sector), they identify - in line with various other authors (such as Papadopoulos [16], Genoese et al. [21] and Yuan et al. [18]) - the main cause of overcapacity in the wrong projections of electricity demand. In fact, while in the early 2000s electricity demand was expected to sharply grow in the following years, Figure 1 shows that these forecasts were not correct. Here, we identify another cause of overcapacity, which is often overlooked in the literature: the errors in forecasts of fuel prices. This is shown in Figure 2, where we compare the projections of NG prices in Europe (black lines) to the actual prices in the years 2000-2015 (red line). The analysis reveals that forecasts heavily underestimated the evolution of NG prices, with error factors as high as 3.85 (year 2008). This suggests that, together with expectations of high growth of electricity demand, also expectations of low prices drove the massive investments in NG cogeneration of heat and power (CHP) in the studied period of time, and that the errors of these projections are at the basis of the scarce profitability of such power plants today.

In fact, as widely discussed in previous work by Moret and coauthors [23, 24], over the long time horizons of strategic energy planning (typically 20-50 years), forecasts often prove to be inaccurate; thus, accounting for the uncertainty in such forecasts could prevent from the risk of making wrong investment decisions, which can lead to overcapacity and underutilization of the installed technologies.

1.3 Overcapacity in the literature and our contribution

Some approaches have been proposed for optimal capacity planning: Dugan et al. [25] proposed a new planning method for distributed generation; Pudjianto et al. [26] presented a new planning approach in which the penetration of renewables is not associated with a fossil overcapacity problem; Koltsaklis et al. [27] introduced a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) approach for the long-term energy planning of national power generation systems, and applied it to the case of Greece. More recently, Mokgonyana et al. [28] proposed a model to help power distribution companies determine optimal network location and capacity for renewable energy source; Heuberger et al. [29] introduced a power systems optimization model for national-scale power supply capacity expansion, and applied it to the UK power system accounting for cost learning effects; Quashie et al. [30] presented a bi-level model for a microgrid power and reserve capacity planning, and applied it to the case of a Canadian utility network; Quiroga et al. [31] implemented a MILP model, which determines the optimal expansion plan considering the installation of both large-scale power plants and renewable-based distributed generation. In general, only few papers in the literature tackle the issue of overcapacity in electricity generation systems; additionally, uncertainty is not integrated in the proposed capacity planning

Figure 2: Natural gas import price in Europe: comparison between the World Bank (WB) price forecasts and the actual values for the years 2000-2015. The black lines are the forecasts made in different years. The red line indicates the actual NG price. Source: World Bank group (<http://www.worldbank.org>). Conversion to USD₂₀₁₅ with the GDP deflator from the U.S. Department of Commerce, Bureau of Economic Analysis [22]

methods, despite its widely recognized importance [32].

Historically, *stochastic programming (SP)* is the “traditional” approach [33] for integrating uncertainties in optimization models. In a nutshell, SP optimizes the expected value of the objective over all the possible realizations of uncertainty (modeled as a scenario tree), under the fundamental assumption that the probability density functions (PDFs) of the uncertain parameters are known [34]. The main limitations of SP are the difficulties in defining PDFs for the uncertain parameters [34], and thus the scenarios, and the fact that it quickly leads to intractable model sizes [33]. One alternative way of considering uncertainty in energy planning models is via *robust optimization*. First proposed by Soyster [35], and later extended by Ben-Tal and Nemirovski [36] and Bertsimas and Sim [37] among others, the basic idea behind RO is to ensure protection against worst-case realizations of uncertainty. The advantage of RO compared to SP is that it is less computationally demanding and it does not require the definition of PDFs for the uncertain parameters, as it suffices to provide lower/upper bounds to characterize uncertainties. Despite an increasing trend in the last years, the use of RO methods is still rather limited in the energy field. Furthermore, applications are normally limited to electricity dispatch problems [38, 39, 40, 41, 42], i.e. they do not consider the entire energy system.

Figure 3: Energy flows in Switzerland in the year 2035: cost optimal deterministic solution. All values are in TWh.

In the present paper, we apply the complete RO framework we presented in [3] (which we briefly recall in Section 2.1.1) to a real-world energy planning problem to answer the specific research question: “*Can robust investment strategies reduce the risk of overcapacity in national power systems?*”. Concretely, we apply the robust decision-support method of Moret et al. [3] to handle *all* uncertainty sources in the Swiss energy system model presented in [24]², and we show how robust energy strategies can prevent from overcapacity.

In its deterministic formulation, the model in [24] represents an energy system, including electricity, heating and mobility, with a multiperiod formulation accounting for seasonality and energy storage. Given the end-use energy demand, the efficiency and cost of energy conversion technologies, the availability and cost of energy resources, the energy model identifies the optimal investment and operation strategies to meet the demand and minimize the total annual cost of the energy system.

Figure 3 illustrates the cost optimal configuration of the Swiss energy system in 2035 in the *deterministic* case, i.e. with all the parameters at nominal value. Following the phase out of nuclear power plants [45], energy supply is dominated by fossil fuels, and in particular by NG (109 TWh/y), burned in CCGT power plants for electricity production and in boilers for heat supply. The high share of fossils, due to their low prices, leads to total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of 39.9 MtCO₂-eq., while renewables and efficient conversion technologies (such as electrical heat pumps (HPs) and CHP) play a marginal role in this scenario. In the next sections, we assess how this deterministic energy strategy changes when considering uncertainty, and in particular whether the inclusion of uncertainty in the energy planning process using RO can limit the risk of generating overcapacity in the energy system.

The paper presents the following contributions:

- The application of a new RO method allowing the consideration of uncertainties in the strategic energy planning of national power systems, which is novel in the literature.
- A comparison between such novel approach and the standard, deterministic decision-making approach.
- The in-depth analysis of the overcapacity in Europe and its causes presented in this section; in particular, we identify the errors in forecasts of fuel prices as a cause of overcapacity.
- The provision of all the data used for the analysis as well as of the full robust formulation of the open-source model in the extensive Supplementary Material.

2 Methodology: a two-step rolling horizon approach

Figure 4 offers an overview of the methodology and numerical studies we designed to answer our research question. We use a two-step rolling horizon approach: first, we generate an initial investment strategy (indicated as \mathbf{F}^* , with \mathbf{F} being the decision variable that represents the installed size of each technology); then, we assess the adaptation of this investment strategy to future uncertainty realizations and the associated risks of overcapacity using a simulation-based approach.

²The model is available open-source at <https://github.com/energyscope/EnergyScope/tree/v1.0> and is used in the online platform <http://energyscope.ch> [43, 44]

Figure 4: Overview of the two-step methodology.

2.1 Definition of the initial investment strategy

In this work, we compare three initial investment strategies defined using three different decision-making criteria, respectively: *i*) the *deterministic* strategy, which does not consider uncertainty and assumes nominal values for all parameters (i.e. perfect hindsight for the future); *ii*) the *worst-case* strategy, assuming that all uncertain parameters will take their worst-case values, as in Soyster [35]; *iii*) the *robust* strategy, defined by applying the robust approach of Moret et al. [3] to all uncertain parameters. In the following subsection we briefly recall this robust approach.

2.1.1 The robust approach

As discussed above, RO is seldom applied to energy models. This is often due to the difficulty in incorporating uncertainties in complex deterministic model formulations, initially developed without accounting for uncertainty. In [3] we propose novel developments to deal with two specific features in existing energy models - i.e. *i*) the presence of multiplied uncertain parameters [46] and *ii*) of many uncertainties in the constraints (as highlighted by Hajimiragha et al. [47] and Rager et al. [48]) - which make it difficult to develop robust formulations. In particular, we extend the robust formulation by Bertsimas and Sim [37] to consider such cases. In their approach, Bertsimas and Sim [37] introduce a parameter (Γ_i) that controls the number of parameters taking their worst-case value simultaneously in the *i*-th constraint (containing $|J_i|$ uncertain parameters). If $\Gamma_i = 0$ the deterministic solution is obtained, whereas if $\Gamma_i = |J_i|$ then the fully robust (worst-case) solution is obtained, as in Soyster [35]. The interest is then to evaluate how the solution of the optimization problem changes when varying Γ_i between these two extreme cases.

In [3], we extend their method and apply it to the MILP cost minimization problem presented in [24]. By doing this, we obtain a robust formulation in which all the uncertain parameters

in the objective function - i.e. the discount rate (i_{rate}), the technology lifetime (n), the costs of investment (c_{inv}), operation and maintenance (O&M) (c_{maint}), and resources (c_{op}) - are controlled by one parameter (Γ_{obj}), and the uncertain parameters in the constraints - mainly the capacity factors ($c_{p,t}$), the demand ($endUses_{year}$) and the conversion efficiencies (η) - are associated to two control parameters ($\Gamma_{c_{p,t}}$ and Γ_{lb} , the latter being the most impacting). The robust formulation of the model is reported in its entirety in the Supplementary Material of the present paper to allow reproducibility.

Additionally, in [3] we propose a decision-support method to help planners identify “good” values for these control parameters Γ_i , and thus make a choice among the different possible energy strategies. The idea behind this simulation-based method is summarized as “*first feasibility, then optimality*”. In fact, in a nutshell, the method first ensures *feasibility* in the constraints, and then evaluates *optimality* in the objective; by doing so, it offers solutions which are both feasible and cost-effective, while at the same time limiting the computational requirements. The simulation results in [3] indicate that robust investment strategies are on average marginally more expensive than the deterministic solution, but offer more reliability (e.g. low risk of not meeting demand) and stability over time. Furthermore, the results highlight the interest of generating robust solutions at intermediate protection levels. Thus, in the present analysis the robust investment strategy obtained by setting $\{\Gamma_{obj} = 30; \Gamma_{lb} = 2; \Gamma_{c_{p,t}} = 0\}$ is taken as representative robust solution, and compared with the deterministic and worst-case investment strategies.

2.2 Adaptation: assessing the risk of overcapacity using simulation

Ideally, a strategic investment strategy, once defined (i.e. once the chosen capacity is installed), should not be modified in the future. However, in the reality of national energy systems, it can happen that if a given technology becomes too expensive to be operated, that given technology is shut down and additional investments are made on other alternatives, thus generating an overcapacity. This corresponds to an adaptation of the initial investment strategy which, as widely discussed in the Introduction, is a rather typical issue in the European electricity sector. In optimization under uncertainty applications, these situations can be handled by including in the model the possibility of *recourse*, i.e. of “*reactive actions after the realization of the uncertainty*” [49], such as a change in the investment decision or in the operating strategy as uncertainty gradually unfolds over time. However, the MILP model we use in this study is a *one-stage* model, which does not consider the possibility of recourse. In fact, although recent developments, such as adjustable robust optimization (ARO) [50] and linear decision rules (LDR) [51], allow considering recourse in RO, obtaining robust formulations for multi-stage problems is to date extremely difficult [33] and restricted to a set of tractable functions.

Thus, we adopt a rolling horizon approach and perform simulations to identify adaptation strategies in the second step for a large set of uncertainty realizations. Concretely, the three considered solutions are simulated imposing that $\mathbf{F} \geq \mathbf{F}^*$ for electricity production technologies. This means that in the simulation runs the initial investment decision - $\mathbf{F}^*(j)$ - becomes the lower bound for the installed capacity of the j -th technology. As a consequence, for each simulated vector of uncertain parameters, the initial installed technologies can be left unused, while new additional capacity ($\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$) can be installed and used for electricity production. As an example, if for a given simulation run NG prices are very high, the CCGT plants can be left unused, and other technologies, such as wind turbines or photovoltaic (PV) panels, can be installed to satisfy the electricity demand; this reproduces a typical situation of overcapacity, in which the unused CCGT power plants become a “sunk cost” in the energy system.

The simulation results are then evaluated using the indicator $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$, defined in Eq. (1).

$$\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}(j) = \frac{1}{n_{runs}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{runs}} \mathbf{F}(j)_i - \mathbf{F}^*(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \quad (1)$$

For a given electricity production technology j , $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}(j)$ is the average additional installed capacity compared to the initial investment decision, $\mathbf{F}^*(j)$. High values of $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$ indicate that the evaluated investment strategy needs major adjustments in the future; low values of $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$ indicate that the initial investment decision is rather stable and is unlikely to require major future modifications.

Additionally, as the choice of relying on electricity imports is an integrating part of the energy strategy, also for electricity imports the lower bound in the simulations is set to the amount imported in the robust solutions, i.e. $\mathbf{Elec}_{imports} \geq \mathbf{Elec}_{imports}^*$. Thus, a second performance indicator is the average additional yearly electricity imports, $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{Elec}_{imports}}$, defined in Eq. (2).

$$\overline{\Delta\mathbf{Elec}_{imports}} = \frac{1}{n_{runs}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{runs}} \mathbf{Elec}_{imports}_i - \mathbf{Elec}_{imports}^* \quad (2)$$

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Initial investment strategies

In Figure 5 and Table 2, we compare the three initial investment strategies - deterministic, robust and worst-case - defined as in Section 2.1. In particular, in Figure 5 the bars on the left represent the total initial installed capacities \mathbf{F}^* ; the bars on the right represent the available capacities \mathbf{F}^*c_p , accounting for the yearly capacity factors (c_p) of the different technologies. As expected, in the figure the available installed capacity increases from left to right: a more conservative decision-making approach corresponds to a higher initial installed capacity, which guarantees a better protection against future adversities.

Table 2: Characterization of the three representative energy system configurations (deterministic, robust, worst-case) compared in this work: heat supply, penetration of renewables and electricity imports.

Solution	Boilers [GW _{th}]	Elec HPs [GW _{th}]	Solar Th. [GW _{th}]	Deep Geo [GW _{th}]	%Dhn [-]	Renewables ^a [TWh/y]	$\mathbf{Elec}_{imports}^*$ [TWh _e /y]
Deterministic	22.3	0.7	0	0.25	0.10	2.8	0
Robust	13.0	10.4	0.61	1.38	0.25	27.4	9.4
Worst-case	21.0	0.9	0	0.37	0.14	13.7	0

^aIncluding PV, wind, new hydro dam and run-of-river plants, deep geothermal, solar thermal

As previously mentioned and shown by the Sankey diagram in Figure 3, the deterministic investment strategy mostly relies on NG CCGT (3 GW_e) for electricity production, and features a low penetration of renewables and efficient technologies also for heat supply. The robust strategy, as typically observed in RO, is more diversified: for electricity supply it features a significant share of renewables (wind, solar PV, new investments in hydro), together with limited investments in fossil fuels (1 GW_e), CHP and a share of electricity imports; for heat supply it is characterized by a higher penetration of renewables (solar thermal and deep geothermal), of district heating network (DHN) and of efficient technologies (such as HPs). The worst-case

Figure 5: Electricity supply mix for the three investment strategies we compare in this work: deterministic, robust and worst-case. Left column: total installed capacity (\mathbf{F}^*); right column: available installed capacity ($\mathbf{F}^* c_p$), where c_p is the yearly capacity factor for the different technologies, taken from [24]. The graph does not include existing hydroelectric dams (8.08 GW_e) and run-of-river plants (3.8 GW_e), which are common to all solutions.

solution relies for electricity supply on CCGT (1 GW_e), wind, and CHP, while for heat supply it is similar to the deterministic solution. In general, the deterministic and the worst-case solutions are more fossil-based strategies, while the robust strategy is characterized by a higher penetration of renewables. The costs of these three initial strategies are discussed in the next section together with the corresponding adaptation costs.

3.2 Adaptation: additional investments and operations

As discussed in Section 2.2, in the reality of energy systems the investment strategy can be adapted as uncertainty gradually unfolds over time. Thus, following the methodology described above, the three studied energy system configurations are simulated $n_{runs} = 10000$ times fixing $\mathbf{F} \geq \mathbf{F}^*$ for electricity production technologies and $\mathbf{Elec}_{imports} \geq \mathbf{Elec}_{imports}^*$, and sampling the values of the uncertain parameters from uniform distributions over the entire uncertainty range. The considered uncertain parameters are: the discount rate (i_{rate}); the technology lifetime (n); the costs of investment (c_{inv}), O&M (c_{maint}), and resources (c_{op}); the capacity factor of renewables ($c_{p,t}$); the energy demand ($endUses_{year}$); the efficiency of technologies (η). The uncertainty ranges, taken from [23], are reported in Table 3. By doing this, overcapacity is allowed in the electricity sector.

The simulation results are reported in Figure 6 and in Table 5. The figure shows that, in the case of the deterministic solution, the total average additional installed capacity in the system is $\sum_{j \in TECH} \Delta \mathbf{F}(j) = 2.14$ GW_e, resulting from new installations of wind turbines (1.02 GW_e), PV (0.62 GW_e), coal (0.4 GW_e), and smaller contributions from hydro run-of-river and CCGT power plants. In terms of capital investment, Table 4 shows that this leads to addi-

Table 3: Ranges of uncertainty (relative to the nominal values) for the uncertain parameters in the simulation study reported in Tables 4, Table 5, Table 6 and Figure 6. Ranges are taken from [23].

Parameter	Range of variation	
	min	max
i_{rate}	-46.2%	46.2%
$c_{inv,mature}$	-21.6%	21.6%
$c_{inv,new}$	-39.6%	39.6%
c_{inv} (HYDRO DAM)	-21.6%	73.8%
c_{inv} (Thermal plants)	-21.6%	25.0%
c_{inv} (WIND)	-21.6%	22.9%
c_{inv} (District Heating Network)	-39.3%	39.3%
c_{inv} (Geothermal)	-39.7%	62.1%
c_{maint}	-48.2%	35.7%
n	-26.5%	26.5%
$c_{op,local}$	-2.9%	2.9%
$c_{op,import}$	-47.3%	89.9%
$endUses_{year}$ (HOUSEHOLDS)	-6.9%	4.3%
$endUses_{year}$ (SERVICES)	-7.4%	4.1%
$endUses_{year}$ (INDUSTRY)	-10.5%	5.9%
$endUses_{year}$ (TRANSPORT)	-3.4%	3.4%
$\eta_{mature,standard}$	-5.7%	5.7%
$\eta_{mature,customized}$	-20.6%	20.6%
$\eta_{new,standard}$	-20.8%	20.8%
$\eta_{new,customized}$	-28.7%	28.7%
$c_{p,t}$	-11.1%	11.1%

tional investment costs of 3831 MCHF (+29%). At the other extreme, the worst-case solution requires little additional investments (0.2 GW_e), as expected; this is because this solution is generated with an overconservative approach, i.e. by already assuming that all parameters will take their worst-case realization in the future. The robust investment strategy offers a trade-off between these two extreme cases: thanks to a diversification in the electricity supply options and to a higher penetration of renewables, for this solution the additional capacity is limited to 0.64 GW_e, resulting from new installations of PV (0.35 GW_e) and CCGT (0.29 GW_e) power plants. A similar trend is observed for the electricity imports: the additional electricity imports are significantly lower for the robust (+929 GWh/y) and the worst-case (+997 GWh/y) investment strategies than for the deterministic solution (+3285 GWh/y).

Table 4: Additional investment cost (mean \bar{x} and standard deviation σ) for the three representative energy system configurations compared in this work: initial (step I, $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^*$) vs. adapted (step II, $\mathbf{F} \geq \mathbf{F}^*$) investment strategies. In both cases, the model is run $n_{runs} = 10000$ times sampling parameters from the entire uncertainty range, reported in Table 3.

Solution	C_{inv} : \bar{x} (σ) [MCHF]		Δ	$\Delta\%$
	Initial	Adapted		
Deterministic	13116 (941)	16947 (5965)	3831	29.2%
Robust	42637 (2423)	43190 (2722)	553	1.3%
Worst-case	22707 (1417)	23173 (1788)	466	2.1%

Table 5 reports the global economic performance of the three solutions: on the one hand, the robust solution is on average more expensive than the deterministic and the worst-case ones; on the other hand, it has a much lower variability and a negligible risk of constraint violations (e.g. of not meeting the demand). Thus, it offers overall a better protection against

Figure 6: Average additional installed capacity ($\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$) and average additional available installed capacity ($\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}c_p}$) for the three representative energy system configurations compared in this work. Uncertain parameters: i_{rate} , n , c_{inv} , c_{maint} , c_{op} , $c_{p,t}$, $endUses_{year}$, η . Model is run $n_{runs} = 10000$ times using uniform distributions and uncertainty ranges as reported in Table 3.

worst case compared to the deterministic and worst-case solutions. In terms of cost, the robust solution features a much higher investment-to-operating cost ratio: the annualized investment cost represents in fact 29% of the total annual energy system cost for this solution, while the deterministic and worst-case solutions have a 13% and 18% share, respectively.

Table 5: Simulation results for the three representative energy system configurations compared in this work: mean (\bar{x}), standard deviation (σ), $\bar{x} + 3\sigma$ for the objective value \mathbf{C}_{tot} (total annual cost); percentage of constraint violations ($\%_{viol}$); \bar{x} and σ for the total investment (\mathbf{C}_{inv}), O&M (\mathbf{C}_{maint}) and operating cost (\mathbf{C}_{op}). Uncertain parameters: i_{rate} , n , c_{inv} , c_{maint} , c_{op} , $c_{p,t}$, $endUses_{year}$, η . Model is run $n_{runs} = 10000$ times sampling parameters from the entire uncertainty range, reported in Table 3, fixing $\mathbf{F} \geq \mathbf{F}^*$ for electricity production technologies.

Solution	\mathbf{C}_{tot} [MCHF/y]		$\%_{viol}$ [%]	\mathbf{C}_{inv} [MCHF]	\mathbf{C}_{inv} [MCHF/y]	\mathbf{C}_{maint} [MCHF]	\mathbf{C}_{op} [MCHF/y]
	\bar{x} (σ)	$\bar{x} + 3\sigma$		\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)
Deterministic	7644 (1473)	12062	53.54%	16947 (5965)	993 (327)	674 (105)	5977 (1269)
Robust	8492 (918)	11244	0.05%	43190 (2722)	2464 (308)	1074 (97)	4954 (841)
Worst-case	7948 (1426)	12224	0.00%	23173 (1788)	1438 (183)	849 (85)	5661 (1376)

Finally, we can assess overcapacity in these three cases. Figure 6 shows that the deterministic solution requires major adjustments (i.e. additional investments in electricity generation capacity) as uncertainty unfolds over time. Table 6 complements this information by evaluating the amount of overcapacity in the energy system. This is done by comparing the theoretical electricity production potential (considering the yearly c_p of the different technologies) with the actual electricity production in the three cases. The robust strategy generates the lowest levels of overcapacity (6.14 TWh_e/y), while the deterministic strategy the highest (10.25 TWh_e/y).

The main reason of this is that, as shown in Figure 3 and in Figure 6, the deterministic strategy strongly relies on NG CCGT power plants, with 3 GW_e installed leading to a theoretical potential of 22.3 TWh_e/y³. The simulations results show that when considering uncertainty the use of these power plants is sharply reduced: the capacity factor drops to 50.5%, i.e. 4429 h/y of full load operation equivalent. In fact, with higher than expected NG prices, the CCGT power plants become too expensive to operate, and thus it is more convenient to shut them down and install other technologies (such as PV panels and wind turbines) to produce electricity.

Table 6: Overcapacity in the three energy system configurations (deterministic, robust, worst-case): theoretical potential for electricity production vs. actual electricity production. Model is run $n_{runs} = 10000$ times sampling parameters from the entire uncertainty range, reported in Table 3.

Solution	Electricity production [TWh _e /y]		
	Capacity	Actual	Overcapacity (Δ)
Deterministic	62.36	52.10	10.25
Robust	63.02	56.88	6.14
Worst-case	63.24	54.86	8.38

Overall, by adopting a probabilistic approach to RO, based on the method proposed by Bertsimas and Sim [37], the robust investment strategy requires less modifications than the deterministic strategy (-70% for $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$), and also lower risks of generating overcapacity in the system (-40%).

3.2.1 Case study: overcapacity in the case of Europe

In this last numerical experiment, we evaluate whether our method is able to realistically reproduce the dynamics that led to overcapacity in Europe in the last two decades. To do this, we focus on the two parameters which, as discussed in the Introduction, were its root causes: fuel prices (c_{op}) and electricity demand ($endUses_{year}(Elec.)$). In particular, to reproduce the dynamics observed in the last two decades in Europe, we assume that forecasts underestimate fuel prices (i.e. fuel prices will be higher than expected), and overestimate electricity demand (i.e. electricity demand will be lower than expected). Concretely, we simulate again the model $n_{runs} = 10000$ times fixing $\mathbf{F} \geq \mathbf{F}^*$ for electricity production technologies and $\mathbf{Elec}_{imports} \geq \mathbf{Elec}_{imports}^*$, but this time sampling the values of the uncertain parameters from uniform distributions over the uncertainty ranges reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Ranges of uncertainty (relative to the nominal values) for the uncertain parameters in the simulation study reported in Table 8, Table 9 and Figure 7 (from [23]). The uncertainty ranges realistically reproduce the dynamics that led to overcapacity in Europe in the last two decades.

Parameter	Range of variation	
	min	max
$c_{op,local}$	0%	2.9%
$c_{op,import}$	0%	89.9%
$endUses_{year}(Elec., HOUSEHOLDS)$	-6.9%	0%
$endUses_{year}(Elec., SERVICES)$	-7.4%	0%
$endUses_{year}(Elec., INDUSTRY)$	-10.5%	0%

³Assuming $c_p = 0.85$ [24], corresponding to 7446 h/y of full load operation equivalent

Figure 7: Average additional installed capacity ($\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$) and average additional available installed capacity ($\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}_{c_p}$) for the three representative energy system configurations compared in this work. Uncertain parameters: c_{op} , $endUses_{year}(Elec.)$. Model is run $n_{runs} = 10000$ times using uniform distributions and uncertainty ranges as reported in Table 7.

The simulation results are reported in Figure 7. The figure shows that, on the one hand, in the case of the deterministic solution, the total average additional installed capacity in the system is of $\sum_{j \in TECH} \overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}(j) = 5.06 \text{ GW}_e$, given by new installations of wind turbines (4.01 GW_e), PV (0.6 GW_e), hydro run-of-river (0.4 GW_e) and coal (0.04 GW_e) power plants. In terms of capital investment, these additional investments are equivalent to the installation of 10 new large traditional power plants. On the other hand, the worst-case solution does not require additional capacity, as expected. The robust investment strategy offers also in this case a trade-off between these two extreme strategies: for this solution the additional installed capacity is limited to 0.63 GW_e , resulting from new installations of PV (0.48 GW_e) and CCGT (0.14 GW_e) power plants. Table 8 shows the economic performance of the three solutions in this last simulation study: in comparison to the previous results in Table 5, the robust solution is now only 3% more expensive on average than the deterministic solution, while still offering a better protection against worst case. This is mostly due to the additional investment costs in the deterministic solution, which sum up to a total increase of 9904 MCHF (+76%).

Looking at the global overcapacity in the system (Table 9), we observe that our simulation-based approach is able to reproduce well the dynamics which led to overcapacity in Europe in the last two decades. This is particularly evident for the deterministic strategy which, as previously discussed, relies on 3 GW_e of CCGT power plants for electricity production. In these last simulations, the capacity factor of CCGT further drops to 36.5%, i.e. 3199 h/y of full load operation equivalent, leading to a total overcapacity of 12.82 TWh_e/y in the energy system. This is because, once again, higher than expected NG prices make the CCGT power plants too expensive to operate. This is similar to what happened in Europe in the last decades, with installed CCGT power plants left unused because non-economical to operate, new technologies

Table 8: Simulation results for the three representative energy system configurations compared in this work: mean (\bar{x}), standard deviation (σ), $\bar{x} + 3\sigma$ for the objective value \mathbf{C}_{tot} (total annual cost); percentage of constraint violations ($\%_{\text{viol}}$); \bar{x} and σ for the total investment (\mathbf{C}_{inv}), O&M ($\mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}$) and operating cost (\mathbf{C}_{op}). Uncertain parameters: c_{op} , $\text{endUses}_{\text{year}}(\text{Elec.})$. Model is run $n_{\text{runs}} = 10000$ times sampling parameters from uncertainty ranges reported in Table 7.

Solution	\mathbf{C}_{tot} [MCHF/y]		$\%_{\text{viol}}$ [%]	\mathbf{C}_{inv} [MCHF]	\mathbf{C}_{inv} [MCHF/y]	$\mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}$ [MCHF]	\mathbf{C}_{op} [MCHF/y]
	\bar{x} (σ)	$\bar{x} + 3\sigma$		\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)	\bar{x} (σ)
Deterministic	9662 (880)	12302	0%	23021 (6565)	1350 (371)	797 (84)	7516 (552)
Robust	9999 (520)	11560	0%	42342 (1137)	2360 (61)	1145 (14)	6494 (499)
Worst-case	9800 (883)	12448	0%	21998 (189)	1348 (9)	899 (2)	7553 (881)

being installed and thus overcapacity being generated in the electric power sector. Also in this case, the robust investment strategy requires less modifications (-88% for $\overline{\Delta\mathbf{F}}$) and also offers lower risks of generating overcapacity in the system (-58%) compared to the deterministic strategy.

Table 9: Overcapacity in the three energy system configurations: theoretical potential for electricity production vs. actual electricity production. Model is run $n_{\text{runs}} = 10000$ times sampling parameters from the uncertainty ranges reported in Table 7.

Solution	Electricity production [TWh _e /y]		
	Capacity	Actual	Overcapacity (Δ)
Deterministic	66.74	53.93	12.82
Robust	62.03	56.54	5.49
Worst-case	62.38	55.07	7.31

These results allow us to finally answer our research question: “*Can robust investment strategies reduce the risk of overcapacity in national power systems?*”. Our results indicate an affirmative response. In fact, our results show that the classical, deterministic energy planning approach, which does not consider uncertainty, is likely to require major adjustments to the investment strategy in the future, generating as a consequence overcapacity in the energy system. The robust solutions, i.e. the solutions generated by using RO methods, by accounting for uncertainty in the planning process, show a significantly lower risk of overcapacity. In particular, a good trade-off is offered by the investment strategy obtained using the method we presented in [3], which guarantees a low risk of overcapacity as well as a lower variability in terms of economic performance compared to the other solutions, though at the price of a marginally higher average total cost. In this regard, it needs to be underlined that in a real-world situation the costs associated to overcapacity might be much higher than the ones considered in the present work. In fact, in this study we did not account, for example, for costs related to decommissioning of the unused power plants or for other penalties (related for example to long-term contracts, subsidies, environmental impacts, etc.) which depend on the specific cases. Thus, the additional investment costs we calculated for the deterministic solution are very likely to represent a - rather optimistic - lower bound to the real costs generated by such drastic changes in the energy strategy.

Overall, our results confirm the interest of probabilistic RO approaches such as the one we presented in [3], as interesting energy system configurations both in terms of robustness and cost-effectiveness - and with a high penetration of renewables and efficient technologies - are obtained at medium protection levels. This example is relevant for energy planners, as it shows that, when considering uncertainty, policies reducing the dependency on fossil fuels can also limit

the risk of overcapacity, which would result in additional financial as well as environmental costs.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we addressed the issue of overcapacity in national power systems, with a particular focus on the case of Europe. We presented an in-depth analysis of the overcapacity situation in various European countries, and discussed the main factors which caused it in the last two decades. Along with other factors - such as the fear of power shortages and the lack of appropriate coordination of government policies - our analysis suggests that errors in forecasts of electricity demand and fuel prices significantly contributed to generating such overcapacity. Second, we assessed whether accounting for uncertainty of these forecasts in the energy planning process, in this case via robust optimization, can reduce the risk of generating overcapacity in national power systems. To do this, we applied the novel robust optimization framework we presented in [3] to a real-world strategic energy planning problem, and compared it to the standard, deterministic decision-making method, which does not consider uncertainties, using a simulation-based approach.

The results show that the robust investment strategies - which, in our case, feature a higher penetration of renewables and efficient technologies - are more stable than the deterministic solution when faced with uncertainties, i.e. less likely to require major future modifications leading to overcapacity. In fact, our numerical studies show that the robust investment strategies require less modifications (up to -88%) and feature a significantly lower risk of generating overcapacity (up to -58%) compared to the deterministic approach; in terms of cost, the robust investment strategy is marginally (3%-11%) more expensive on average than the deterministic solution, while offering a better protection against worst case. Overall, as the simulation-based approach adopted in this work is able to reproduce well the dynamics observed in the case Europe, our results suggest that the consideration of uncertainty in the energy planning practice in the last two decades could have possibly limited the large overcapacity in the European power systems, which resulted in additional financial as well as environmental costs.

Acronyms and abbreviations

CCGT	Combined cycle gas turbine
CHP	Cogeneration of heat and power
DHN	District heating network
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HP	Heat pump
MILP	Mixed-integer linear programming
NG	Natural gas
O&M	Operation and maintenance
PDF	Probability density function
PV	Photovoltaic
RO	Robust optimization
SP	Stochastic programming

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Overcapacity in European power systems: analysis and robust optimization approach

Supplementary Material

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1 Deterministic model formulation

The mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model is presented in [1] and available at <https://github.com/energyscope/EnergyScope/tree/v1.0>. In this section, we recall the entire formulation. The input data are available online and fully documented in [1], Appendix A.

1.1 Sets, parameters, variables

Figure 1 is a visual representation of the sets of the proposed formulation with their relative indices used throughout the paper; Table 1 lists the parameters; Table 2 and Table 3 list and describe the independent and dependent decision variables, respectively. Units should be proportionally scaled based on the specific application.

Figure 1: Visual representation of the sets and indices of the MILP framework. Abbreviations: space heating (SH), hot water (HW), temperature (T), mobility (MOB)

Table 1: Parameter list with description. Set indices as in Figure 1

Parameter	Units	Description
$d_{year}(eui, s)$	[GWh/y] ^a	Annual end-uses in energy services per sector
$endUsesInput(eui)$	[GWh/y] ^a	Total annual end-uses in energy services
$\tau(tech)$	[-]	Investment cost annualization factor
i_{rate}	[-]	Real discount rate
$\%_{public,min}, \%_{public,max}$	[-]	Upper and lower limit to $\%_{Public}$
$\%_{rail,min}, \%_{rail,max}$	[-]	Upper and lower limit to $\%_{Rail}$
$\%_{dhn,min}, \%_{dhn,max}$	[-]	Upper and lower limit to $\%_{Dhn}$
$t_{op}(t)$	[h]	Time periods duration
$\%_{lighting}(t)$	[-]	Yearly share (adding up to 1) of lighting end-uses
$\%_{sh}(t)$	[-]	Yearly share (adding up to 1) of SH end-uses
$f(res \cup tech \setminus sto, l)$	[GW] ^b	Input from (< 0) or output to (> 0) layers. $f(i, j) = 1$ if j is main output layer for technology/resource i
$f_{ref}(tech)$	[GW] ^{bc}	Reference size with respect to main output
$c_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF/GW] ^{bc}	Technology specific investment cost
$c_{maint}(tech)$	[MCHF/GW/y] ^{bc}	Technology specific yearly O&M cost
$gwp_{constr}(tech)$	[ktCO ₂ -eq./GW] ^{bc}	Technology construction specific GHG emissions
$n(tech)$	[y]	Technology lifetime
$f_{min}, f_{max}(tech)$	[GW] ^{bc}	Min./max. installed size of the technology
$f_{min,\%}, f_{max,\%}(tech)$	[-]	Min./max. relative share of a technology in a layer
$avail(res)$	[GWh/y]	Resource yearly total availability
$c_{p,t}(tech, t)$	[-]	Period capacity factor (default 1)
$c_p(tech)$	[-]	Yearly capacity factor
$c_{op}(res, t)$	[MCHF/GWh]	Specific cost of resources
$gwp_{op}(res)$	[ktCO ₂ -eq./GWh]	Specific GHG emissions of resources
$\eta_{s,in}, \eta_{s,out}(sto, l)$	[-]	Efficiency [0; 1] of storage input from/output to layer. Set to 0 if storage not related to layer.
$\%_{loss}(eut)$	[-]	Losses [0; 1] in the networks (grid and DHN)
$\%_{PeakDHN}$	[-]	Ratio peak/max. average DHN heat demand

Table 2: Independent decision variable list with description. All variables are continuous and non-negative, unless otherwise indicated.

Variable	Units	Description
$\%_{Public}$	[-]	Ratio [0; 1] public mobility over total passenger mobility
$\%_{Rail}$	[-]	Ratio [0; 1] rail transport over total freight transport
$\%_{Dhn}$	[-]	Ratio [0; 1] centralized over total low-temperature heat
$F(tech)$	[GW] ^{bc}	Installed capacity with respect to main output
$F_t(tech \cup res, t)$	[GW] ^{bc}	Operation in each period
$S_{in}, S_{out}(sto, l, t)$	[GW]	Input to/output from storage units
$Y_{Solar}(tech) \in \{0; 1\}$	[-]	If 1, $tech$ is backup technology for decentralized solar

^a [Mpkkm] (millions of passenger-km) for passenger, [Mtkm] (millions of ton-km) for freight mobility end-uses^b [Mpkkm/h] for passenger, [Mtkm/h] for freight mobility end-uses^c [GWh] if $tech \in STO$

Table 3: Dependent decision variable list with description. All variables are continuous and non-negative, unless otherwise indicated.

Variable	Units	Description
$\mathbf{D}(l, t)$	[GW] ^a	End-uses demand. Set to 0 if $l \notin EUT$
$\mathbf{N}(tech) \in \mathbb{N}$	[-]	Number of installed units of size f_{ref}
\mathbf{C}_{tot}	[MCHF/y]	Total annual cost of the energy system
$\mathbf{C}_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF]	Technology total investment cost
$\mathbf{C}_{maint}(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Technology yearly O&M cost
$\mathbf{C}_{op}(res)$	[MCHF/y]	Total cost of resources
\mathbf{GWP}_{tot}	[ktCO ₂ -eq./y]	Total yearly GHG emissions of the energy system
$\mathbf{GWP}_{constr}(tech)$	[ktCO ₂ -eq.]	Technology construction GHG emissions
$\mathbf{GWP}_{op}(res)$	[ktCO ₂ -eq./y]	Total GHG emissions of resources
$\mathbf{Loss}(eut, t)$	[GW]	Losses in the networks (grid and DHN)

^a[Mpkm/h] for passenger, [Mtkm/h] for freight mobility end-uses

1.2 Constraints

The model formulation is expressed by the equations in Figure 2 and Eq. 1-20.

1.2.1 End-uses demand

In the energy modeling practice, the energy demand is often expressed in terms of *final energy consumption (FEC)*. FEC is defined as “the energy which reaches the final consumer’s door” [2]. In other words, the FEC is the amount of input fuel needed to satisfy the *end-use demand (EUD)* in energy services. As an example, in the case of decentralized heat production with a natural gas (NG) boiler, the FEC is the amount of NG consumed by the boiler; the EUD is the amount of heat produced by the boiler, i.e. the heating service needed by the final user. The input to the proposed modeling framework is the EUD in energy services, represented as the sum of three components: electricity, heating and mobility; this also replaces the classical sector-based representation of energy demand. This modeling choice has two advantages. First, it introduces a clear distinction between demand and supply. On the one hand, the demand concerns the definition of the end-uses, i.e. the requirements in energy services (e.g. the mobility needs). On the other hand, the supply concerns the choice of the energy conversion technologies to supply these services (e.g. the types of vehicles used to satisfy the mobility needs). Based on the technology choice, the same EUD can be satisfied with a different FEC, depending on the efficiency of the chosen energy conversion technology. Second, it facilitates the inclusion in the model of electric technologies for heating and transportation (such as heat pumps and electric vehicles).

Figure 2: \mathbf{D} calculation starting from yearly demand model input ($endUsesInput$)

$$\min \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{j \in \text{TECH}} (\tau(j) \mathbf{C}_{\text{inv}}(j) + \mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}(j)) + \sum_{i \in \text{RES}} \mathbf{C}_{\text{op}}(i)^1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tau(j) = \frac{i_{\text{rate}}(i_{\text{rate}} + 1)^{n(j)}}{(i_{\text{rate}} + 1)^{n(j)} - 1} \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{inv}}(j) = c_{\text{inv}}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}(j) = c_{\text{maint}}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{constr}}(j) = gwp_{\text{constr}}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (5)$$

$$f_{\text{min}}(j) \leq \mathbf{F}(j) \leq f_{\text{max}}(j) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{N}(j) f_{\text{ref}}(j) = \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t) \leq \mathbf{F}(j) c_{p,t}(j, t) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH}, \forall t \in T \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t) t_{\text{op}}(t) \leq \mathbf{F}(j) c_p(j) \sum_{t \in T} t_{\text{op}}(t) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{op}}(i) = \sum_{t \in T} c_{\text{op}}(i, t) \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(i, t) t_{\text{op}}(t) \quad \forall i \in \text{RES} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{op}}(i) = \sum_{t \in T} gwp_{\text{op}}(i, t) \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(i, t) t_{\text{op}}(t) \quad \forall i \in \text{RES} \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(i, t) t_{\text{op}}(t) \leq \text{avail}(i) \quad \forall i \in \text{RES} \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \text{RES} \cup \text{TECH} \setminus \text{STO}} f(i, l) \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(i, t) + \sum_{j \in \text{STO}} (\mathbf{S}_{\text{out}}(j, l, t) - \mathbf{S}_{\text{in}}(j, l, t)) - \mathbf{D}(l, t) = 0^1 \quad \forall l \in L, \forall t \in T \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t) = \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t-1) + t_{\text{op}}(t).$$

$$\left(\sum_{l \in L | \eta_{s,\text{in}}(j,l) > 0} \mathbf{S}_{\text{in}}(j, l, t) \eta_{s,\text{in}}(j, l) - \sum_{l \in L | \eta_{s,\text{out}}(j,l) > 0} \mathbf{S}_{\text{out}}(j, l, t) / \eta_{s,\text{out}}(j, l) \right) \quad \forall j \in \text{STO}, \forall t \in T \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{in}}(j, l, t) (\lceil \eta_{s,\text{in}}(j, l) \rceil - 1) = 0 \quad \forall j \in \text{STO}, \forall l \in L, \forall t \in T \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{\text{out}}(j, l, t) (\lceil \eta_{s,\text{out}}(j, l) \rceil - 1) = 0 \quad \forall j \in \text{STO}, \forall l \in L, \forall t \in T \quad (16)$$

$$\left[\sum_{l \in L | \eta_{s,\text{in}}(j,l) > 0} \mathbf{S}_{\text{in}}(j, l, t) / m(j, l, t) \right] + \left[\sum_{l \in L | \eta_{s,\text{out}}(j,l) > 0} \mathbf{S}_{\text{out}}(j, l, t) / m(j, l, t) \right] \leq 1 \quad \forall j \in \text{STO}, \forall t \in T \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{Loss}(eut, t) = \left(\sum_{i \in \text{RES} \cup \text{TECH} \setminus \text{STO} | f(i, eut) > 0} f(i, eut) \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(i, t) \right) \%_{\text{loss}}(eut) \quad \forall eut \in \text{EUT}, \forall t \in T \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t) + \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(k, t) \mathbf{Y}_{\text{Solar}}(j) \geq \frac{\text{endUsesInput}(\text{HeatLowTSH}) \frac{\%_{\text{sh}}(t)}{t_{\text{op}}(t)} + \frac{\text{endUsesInput}(\text{HeatLowTHW})}{\sum_{t \in T} t_{\text{op}}(t)}}{\text{endUsesInput}(\text{HeatLowTSH}) + \text{endUsesInput}(\text{HeatLowTHW})} \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j, t) t_{\text{op}}(t)$$

$$k = \text{Dec}_{\text{Solar}}, \forall j \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(\text{HeatLowTDec}) \setminus \{k\}, \forall t \in T \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \text{TECH}} \mathbf{Y}_{\text{Solar}}(j) \leq 1 \quad (20)$$

¹These equations are modified in the robust formulation (Section 2).

Figure 2 shows the constraints relative to the calculation of the EUD in each period t (\mathbf{D}) starting from the projected total yearly demand ($endUsesInput$, input from demand-side model) summed across the different energy sectors (households, services, industry, transport). Electricity end-uses result from the sum of the electricity-only demand, assumed constant throughout the year, and the demand for lighting, distributed across the periods according to $\%_{lighting}$. Low-temperature heat demand results from the sum of yearly demand for hot water (HW), evenly shared across the year, and space heating (SH), distributed across the periods according to $\%_{sh}$. The percentage repartition between centralized (district heating network (DHN)) and decentralized heat demand is defined by the variable $\%_{Dhn}$. High temperature process heat and mobility demand are evenly distributed across the periods. Passenger mobility demand is expressed in passenger-kilometers (pkms), freight transportation demand is in ton-kilometers (tkms). The variables $\%_{Public}$ and $\%_{Rail}$ define the penetration of public transportation in passenger mobility and of train in freight, respectively.

1.2.2 Total cost and GHG emissions

In the proposed formulation, the objective is the minimization of the total annual cost of the energy system (\mathbf{C}_{tot}), defined as the sum of the annualized investment and operation and maintenance (O&M) cost (\mathbf{C}_{maint}) of technologies, and the operating cost of resources (\mathbf{C}_{op}) (Eq. 1). The total investment cost (\mathbf{C}_{inv}) of each technology results from the multiplication of its specific investment cost (c_{inv}) and installed size (\mathbf{F}), the latter defined with respect to the main end-uses output type (Eq. 3). \mathbf{C}_{inv} is annualized with the factor τ , calculated based on the interest rate (i_{rate}) and the technology lifetime (n) (Eq. 2). The total O&M cost is calculated in the same way (Eq. 4). Upper and lower limits to the installed capacity of each technology are set by f_{max} and f_{min} , respectively. The latter allows accounting for old technologies still existing in the target year (Eq. 6). Eq. 7 forces the number of installed units of a technology to be an integer multiple (\mathbf{N}) of the reference size f_{ref} . The total cost of resources is calculated as the sum of the use over different periods multiplied by the period duration (t_{op}) and the specific cost of the resource (c_{op}) (Eq. 10).

The global annual greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are calculated using a life cycle assessment (LCA) approach, i.e. taking into account emissions of technologies and resources “from cradle to grave”. For climate change, the natural choice as indicator is the global warming potential (GWP), expressed in ktCO₂-eq./year. In Eq. 21 the total yearly emissions of the system (\mathbf{GWP}_{tot}) are defined as the sum of the emissions related to the construction and end-of-life of the energy conversion technologies (\mathbf{GWP}_{constr}), allocated to one year based on the technology lifetime, and the emissions related to resources (\mathbf{GWP}_{op}).

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{tot} = \sum_{j \in TECH} \frac{\mathbf{GWP}_{constr}(j)}{n(j)} + \sum_{i \in RES} \mathbf{GWP}_{op}(i) \quad (21)$$

The total emissions related to the construction of technologies are the product of the specific emissions (gwp_{constr}) and the installed size (Eq. 5). The total emissions of resources are the emissions associated to fuels (from cradle to combustion) and imports of electricity. They are calculated as the sum of the use over different periods multiplied by the period duration and the specific emissions of the resource (gwp_{op}) (Eq. 11). Operating emissions of technologies, mainly corresponding to auxiliary materials and maintenance, can also be additionally added to the formulation. As MILP problems have only one objective, \mathbf{GWP}_{tot} can be used as objective instead of \mathbf{C}_{tot} . Alternatively, the two objectives can be combined using the ϵ -constraint method [3]. This method seeks trade-off solutions by formulating a bi-objective

problem in which one of the objectives is minimized, and the other is constrained by an upper value ϵ , which is made vary parametrically.

1.2.3 Operational constraints: layers and storage

The operation of resources and technologies in each period is determined by the decision variable \mathbf{F}_t . The *capacity factor* of technologies is conceptually divided into two components: a capacity factor for each period ($c_{p,t}$) depending on resource availability (e.g. renewables) and a yearly capacity factor (c_p) accounting for technology downtime and maintenance. For a given technology, the definition of only one capacity factor is needed, the other one being fixed to the default value of 1. Eqs. 8 and 9 link the installed size of a technology to its actual use in each period (\mathbf{F}_t) via the two capacity factors, respectively. The total use of resources is limited by the yearly availability (*avail*) (Eq. 12).

Layers are defined as all the elements in the system that need to be balanced in each period, such as resources and end-uses demand. The matrix f defines for all technologies and resources outputs to (positive) and inputs from (negative) layers. Eq. 13 expresses the balance for each layer: all outputs from resources and technologies (including storage) are used to satisfy the EUD or as inputs to other resources and technologies. Figure 3 offers an intuitive representation of the constraint. Each layer can be conceptually thought of as a pool in which the water level must be the same at the end of each period. As an example, the electricity which is imported or produced in the system is used to satisfy the electricity EUD; additionally, it can be stored in hydroelectric dams or used as input to other energy conversion technologies (such as heat pumps or electric vehicles) to satisfy other EUD types.

Figure 3: Conceptual representation of a *layer*: all outputs from resources and technologies (including storage) are used to satisfy end-uses demand or as inputs to other resources and technologies (Eq. 13).

Storage technologies allow storage across different periods and layers. The storage is modeled as a “tank” whose level (\mathbf{F}_t) in period t is equal to the level at the end of the previous period plus input to the storage (\mathbf{S}_{in}) minus output (\mathbf{S}_{out}) in t (Eq. 14). The parameters $\eta_{s,in}$ and $\eta_{s,out}$ define efficiencies for storage inputs and outputs, respectively: if the efficiency is 0 then the storage technology and the layer are incompatible (Eqs. 15-16). Eq. 17, displayed in a

compact non-linear formulation¹, ensures that the storage is not used as a transfer unit within a given period. In the equation, the parameter m must be big enough to ensure that the arguments of the ceiling operators are lower or equal than 1. As an example, $m(j, l, t) = \max \left\{ \frac{f_{max}(j)}{\eta_{s,in}(j,l)t_{op}(t)}, \frac{\eta_{s,out}(j,l)f_{max}(j)}{t_{op}(t)} \right\}$ satisfies this condition.

1.2.4 Other constraints

Losses (**Loss**) are considered for the electricity grid and for the DHN. They are calculated as a percentage ($\%_{loss}$) of the total production and import in the corresponding layers (Eq. 18).

Eq. 19 (also expressed in a compact non-linear formulation) makes the model more realistic by defining the operating strategy for decentralized heating: the relative use of each technology in each period should be constant, except for solar thermal (Dec_{Solar}). If solar thermal is installed, then at maximum one technology is used as backup (Eq. 20).

1.3 Additional constraints for the case study of Switzerland

Eqs. 1-20 and Figure 2 define the main constraints of the MILP model. Eqs. 22-29 are added to simplify the use of the model and adapt it to the specific case study of Switzerland.

Eq. 22 is complementary to Eq. 6, as it expresses the minimum ($f_{min,\%}$) and maximum ($f_{max,\%}$) yearly output shares of each technology for each type of EUD. In fact, for a given technology, assigning a relative share (e.g. boilers providing at least a given percent of the total heat demand) is more intuitive and close to the energy planning practice than limiting its installed size. $f_{min,\%}$ and $f_{max,\%}$ are fixed to 0 and 1, respectively, unless otherwise indicated. Eq. 23 imposes that the share of the different technologies for mobility be the same in each period. The addition of this constraint is motivated by the fact that the investment cost of passenger and freight transport technologies is not accounted for in the model. Eq. 24-25 regulate the functioning of hydroelectric dams in Switzerland, which is further detailed in Appendix A of [1]. Increasing the installed power of the dams, and thus their yearly production, allows also to have a margin for shifting their electricity production across the time periods. This possibility is represented in the model by *StoHydro*, a “storage” technology (with efficiency equal to 1) allowing to shift the production of hydroelectric dams across the different months. Eq. 24 links linearly the storage capacity to the new installed power. Eq. 25 ensures that the shifted production in a given time period does not exceed the electricity production by the dams in that period. Eq. 26 links the DHN size to the total size of the installed centralized energy conversion technologies. To avoid underestimating the cost of centralized heat production, a multiplication factor is introduced to account for peak demand, defined as a $\%_{Peak_{DHN}}$ times the maximum monthly average heat demand (Eq. 27). Based on the data reported in Appendix A in [1], an additional investment cost of 9.4 billion CHF₂₀₁₅ is linked proportionally to the deployment of stochastic renewables (Eq. 28). The power-to-gas storage system is implemented in the model with two conversion units and a liquified natural gas (LNG) storage tank. *PowerToGas* converts electricity to LNG, *GasToPower* converts LNG back to electricity. The investment cost is associated to the *Power2Gas* unit, whose size is the maximum size of the two conversion units.

¹All equations expressed in a compact non-linear form in this chapter (Eqs. 19, 17, 27, 29) can be easily linearized.

$$\sum_{j' \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(eut)} f_{min, \%}(j) \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_t(j', t) t_{op}(t) \leq \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_t(j, t) t_{op}(t) \leq \sum_{j' \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(eut)} f_{max, \%}(j) \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_t(j', t) t_{op}(t) \quad \forall eut \in EUT, \forall j \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(eut) \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_t(j, t) \sum_{t \in T} t_{op}(t) \geq \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{F}_t(j, t) t_{op}(t) \quad \forall j \in \text{TECH OF EUC}(MobPass) \cup \text{TECH OF EUC}(MobFreight), \forall t \in T \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\text{StoHydro}) \leq f_{max}(\text{StoHydro}) \frac{\mathbf{F}(\text{NewHydroDam}) - f_{min}(\text{NewHydroDam})}{f_{max}(\text{NewHydroDam}) - f_{min}(\text{NewHydroDam})} \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{in}(\text{StoHydro}, \text{Elec}, t) \leq \mathbf{F}_t(\text{HydroDam}, t) + \mathbf{F}_t(\text{NewHydroDam}, t) \quad \forall t \in T \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\text{DHN}) \geq \sum_{j \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(\text{HeatLowTDHN})} \mathbf{F}(j) \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \text{TECH OF EUT}(\text{HeatLowTDHN})} \mathbf{F}(j) \geq \%_{PeakDHN} \max_{t \in T} \{ \mathbf{D}(\text{HeatLowTDHN}, t) \} \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\text{Grid}) \geq 1 + \frac{9400}{c_{inv}(\text{Grid})} \frac{\mathbf{F}(\text{Wind}) + \mathbf{F}(\text{PV})}{f_{max}(\text{Wind}) + f_{max}(\text{PV})} \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(\text{Power2Gas}) = \max \{ \mathbf{F}(\text{PowerToGas}); \mathbf{F}(\text{GasToPower}) \} \quad (29)$$

2 Robust model formulation

In this Section, we report the modifications and additions to the deterministic MILP formulation presented in Section 1, needed to obtain the full robust formulation of the model based on the method in [4].

2.1 Sets, parameters, variables

The sets of the robust formulation are the sets reported in Figure 1, i.e. no additional set is defined. Table 4 and 5 report the additional parameters and variables defined in the robust formulation, respectively.

Table 4: Additional parameters defined in the robust formulation, with description. Set indices as in Figure 1

Parameter	Units	Description
$\delta_{dem}(eui, s)$	[GWh/y] ^a	Max. worst-case deviation for d_{year}
$\tau_r = \alpha \frac{i_{rate}}{2}$	[-]	Approximation of τ (1st half)
$\tau_n(tech) = \frac{1}{n(tech)}$	[-]	Approximation of τ (2nd half)
$\alpha = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left[\tau - \frac{1}{n} \right] \frac{2}{i_{rate}}$	[-]	Correction factor for τ_r
δ_{τ_r}	[-]	Max worst-case deviation for τ_r
$\delta_{\tau_n}(tech)$	[-]	Max. worst-case deviation for τ_n
$\delta_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF/GW] ^{bc}	Max. worst-case deviation for c_{inv}
$\delta_{maint}(tech)$	[MCHF/GW] ^{bc}	Max. worst-case deviation for c_{maint}
$\delta_{op}(res)$	[MCHF/GWh]	Max. worst-case deviation for c_{op}
$\delta_{c_{p,t}}(tech, t)$	[-]	Max worst-case deviation for $c_{p,t}$
$\delta_{\eta}(res \cup tech \setminus sto, l)$	[-]	Max. worst-case deviation for η
$\delta_f(res \cup tech \setminus sto, l)$	[GW] ^b	Max. worst-case deviation for f
Γ_{obj}	[-]	control parameter for the objective function
Γ_{lb}	[-]	control parameter for constraint 13
$\Gamma_{c_{p,t}}$	[-]	control parameter for constraint 8

^a [Mpkm] (millions of passenger-km) for passenger, [Mtkm] (millions of ton-km) for freight mobility end-uses

^b [Mpkm/h] for passenger, [Mtkm/h] for freight mobility end-uses

^c [GWh] if $tech \in STO$

Table 5: Additional decision variables defined in the robust formulation, with description. Set indices as in Figure 1. All variables are continuous and non-negative, unless otherwise indicated.

Variable	Units	Description
\mathbf{z}_{obj}	[MCHF/y]	Objective function
$\mathbf{p}_r(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_r
$\mathbf{p}_n(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_n
$\mathbf{p}_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to c_{inv}
$\mathbf{p}_{maint}(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to c_{maint}
$\mathbf{p}_{op}(res, t)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to c_{op}
$\eta_r(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_r, τ_n, c_{inv} [4]
$\eta_n(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_r, τ_n, c_{inv} [4]
$\pi_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_r, τ_n, c_{inv} [4]
$\pi'_{inv}(tech)$	[MCHF/y]	Objective function, relative to τ_r, τ_n, c_{inv} [4]
$\mathbf{y}_{maint}(tech)$	[GW] ^a	Objective function, relative to c_{maint}
$\mathbf{y}_{op}(res, t)$	[GWh]	Objective function, relative to c_{op}
$\mathbf{z}_{lb}(euc \cup res, t)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 13, relative to f and d_{year}
$\mathbf{y}_{lb}(tech \setminus sto, t)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 13, relative to f
$\mathbf{p}_f(tech \setminus sto, euc \cup res, t)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 13, relative to f
$\mathbf{p}_{dem}(eui, s, t)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 13, relative to d_{year}
$\mathbf{z}_{c_{p,t}}(tech)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 8, relative to $c_{p,t}$
$\mathbf{p}_{c_{p,t}}(tech, t)$	[GW] ^a	Constraint 8, relative to $c_{p,t}$

^a [Mpkm/h] for passenger, [Mtkm/h] for freight mobility end-uses

2.2 Constraints

We report here the constraints which are added or modified in the robust formulation.

2.2.1 Objective function

The deterministic objective function (Eq. 1) is replaced by Eqs. 30.

$$\begin{aligned}
\min \quad & \sum_{j \in TECH} (\tau_r + \tau_n(j)) c_{inv}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) + \sum_{j \in TECH} c_{maint}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) + \sum_{i \in RES} \sum_{t \in T} c_{op}(i, t) \mathbf{F}_t(i, t) t_{op}(t) \quad (30) \\
& + \mathbf{z}_{obj} \Gamma_{obj} + \sum_{j \in TECH} (\mathbf{P}_r(j) + \mathbf{P}_n(j) + \mathbf{P}_{inv}(j) + \mathbf{P}_{maint}(j)) + \sum_{i \in RES} \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{P}_{op}(i, t) \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{z}_r + \sum_{j \in TECH} (-\boldsymbol{\eta}_r(j) + \mathbf{P}_r(j)) \geq \delta_{\tau_r} \sum_{j \in TECH} (c_{inv}(j) \mathbf{F}(j)) \\
& \mathbf{z}_n - \boldsymbol{\eta}_n(j) + \mathbf{P}_n(j) \geq \delta_{\tau_n}(j) c_{inv}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \mathbf{z}_{inv} - \boldsymbol{\pi}_{inv}(j) - \boldsymbol{\pi}'_{inv}(j) + \mathbf{P}_{inv}(j) \geq \delta_{inv}(j) (\tau_r + \tau_n(j)) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \boldsymbol{\eta}_r(j) + \boldsymbol{\pi}_{inv}(j) \geq \delta_{\tau_r} \delta_{inv}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \boldsymbol{\eta}_n(j) + \boldsymbol{\pi}'_{inv}(j) \geq \delta_{\tau_n}(j) \delta_{inv}(j) \mathbf{F}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \mathbf{z}_0 + \mathbf{P}_{maint}(j) \geq \delta_{maint}(j) \mathbf{y}_{maint}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \mathbf{F}(j) \leq \mathbf{y}_{maint}(j) \quad \forall j \in TECH \\
& \mathbf{z}_0 + \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{P}_{op}(i, t) \geq \delta_{op}(i) \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{y}_{op}(i, t) \quad \forall i \in RES \\
& \mathbf{F}_t(i, t) t_{op}(t) \leq \mathbf{y}_{op}(i, t) \quad \forall i \in RES, \forall t \in T
\end{aligned}$$

In which $\delta_{\tau_r} = \frac{1}{2} (i_{rate}(\alpha' - \alpha) + \alpha' \delta_{i_{rate}})$, with $\delta_{i_{rate}}$ being the maximum worst case deviation from the nominal value of the interest rate, α being the correction factor for the nominal value of the interest rate, and α' being the correction factor for its worst case value; $\delta_{\tau_n}(j) = \frac{\delta_n(j)}{n(j)(n(j) - \delta_n(j))}$, with $\delta_n(j)$ being the maximum worst case deviation from the nominal value of the technologies' lifetime.

Additional notes:

- As discussed in [4], in this formulation we use the following simplification: $\mathbf{z}_{obj} \Gamma_{obj} = \mathbf{z}_r \Gamma_r + \mathbf{z}_n \Gamma_n + \mathbf{z}_{inv} \Gamma_{inv} + \mathbf{z}_0 \Gamma_0$.
- For coal and NG, in the model we consider the possibility of carbon capture and storage (CCS) by adding "CCS resources". As an example, a standard combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) power plant uses the NG resource as an input, while a CCGT power plant with CCS uses the NG (CCS) resource as an input. This means that there are two instances of the same resource (NG in this case) to account for its different use. When considering cost uncertainty, the cost variation must be identical for the two instances. For NG, this is imposed by Eq. 31, which equivalently applies to coal. See [1] for more details. In this paper, the availability of CCS resources is fixed to 10000 GWh.

$$\mathbf{z}_{obj} + \sum_{t \in T} (\mathbf{P}_{op}(i, t) + \mathbf{P}_{op}(k, t)) \geq \delta_{op}(i) \sum_{t \in T} (\mathbf{y}_{op}(i, t) + \mathbf{y}_{op}(k, t)) \quad i = NG, k = NG \text{ (CCS)} \quad (31)$$

- In Eqs. 30, it is considered that c_{op} varies equally in the different months of the reference year. However, based on global sensitivity analysis (GSA) results in [1], c_{op} is the most impacting parameter on the investment decision. Thus, in this work, c_{op} is made vary gradually towards the worst case ($c_{op} + \delta_{op}$), i.e. in six sequential steps of size $\delta_{op}/6$. Numerical tests show that this choice allows a more gradual transition towards the worst case, without altering the trade-offs between the different robust solutions.

2.2.2 Period capacity factor (constraint 8)

Following the method in [4], Eq. 8 is kept in the formulation. $c_{p,t}$ is indexed over the set of technologies ($TECH$) and the set of periods (T). Summing over T distributes the uncertainty budget over the different periods. This is enforced by the addition of Eqs. 32, in which $\Gamma_{c_{p,t}} \in [0, 12]$ is the protection parameter, $\delta_{c_{p,t}}$ is the maximum worst-case deviation from the nominal value of $c_{p,t}$, $\mathbf{z}_{c_{p,t}}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{c_{p,t}}$ are the dual variables.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in T} (\mathbf{F}_t(j, t) - \mathbf{F}(j)c_{p,t}(j, t)) + \mathbf{z}_{c_{p,t}}(j)\Gamma_{c_{p,t}} + \sum_{t \in T} \mathbf{p}_{c_{p,t}}(j, t) &\leq 0 & \forall j \in TECH \quad (32) \\ \mathbf{z}_{c_{p,t}}(j) + \mathbf{p}_{c_{p,t}}(j, t) &\geq \delta_{c_{p,t}}(j)\mathbf{F}(j) & \forall j \in TECH, \forall t \in T \end{aligned}$$

Formulation 32 groups equally the 60 uncertain parameters into 5 constraints, controlled by the protection parameter $\Gamma_{c_{p,t}}$. When $\Gamma_{c_{p,t}}$ is increased of a unitary step, for each technology the $c_{p,t}$ of an additional period assumes its worst-case realization. To ensure a realistic yearly distribution of $c_{p,t}$ in the uncertain domain, Eq. 33 additionally imposes that, if a given technology is installed, the maximum deviation from the nominal output in a given period be at maximum $\delta_{c_{p,t}}$.

$$\mathbf{F}_t(j, t) \geq \mathbf{F}(j)(c_{p,t}(j, t) - \delta_{c_{p,t}}(j)) \quad \forall j \in TECH, \forall t \in T | c_{p,t}(j, t) < 1 \quad (33)$$

2.2.3 Layer balance: efficiencies and energy demand (constraint 13)

The conversion efficiency of technologies (η) and the yearly energy demand (d_{year}) are accounted for in the layer balance equation (Eq. 13). In total, 52 uncertain instances of η and 15 uncertain instances of d_{year} are considered.

$$\underbrace{\sum_{i \in RES \cup TECH \setminus STO} f(i, l)\mathbf{F}_t(i, t) + \sum_{j \in STO} (\mathbf{S}_{out}(j, l, t) - \mathbf{S}_{in}(j, l, t)) - \mathbf{D}(l, t)}_{\mathbf{LB}} = 0 \quad \forall l \in L, \forall t \in T \quad (13)$$

As discussed in [4], to obtain the robust counterpart, the first step is the relaxation of the equality constraint Eq. 13 to an inequality constraint, i.e. $\mathbf{LB} \geq 0$.

Then, for resource layers, the classical robust formulation in [5] applies (Eqs. 34)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{LB} - \mathbf{z}_{lb}(l, t)\Gamma_{lb} - \sum_{i \in TECH \setminus STO} \mathbf{p}_f(i, l, t) &\geq 0 & \forall l \in L \cap RES, \forall t \in T \quad (34) \\ \mathbf{z}_{lb}(l, t) + \mathbf{p}_f(i, l, t) &\geq \delta_f(i, l)\mathbf{y}_{lb}(i, t) \\ & \forall i \in TECH \setminus STO, \forall l \in L \cap RES, \forall t \in T | f(i, l) < 0 \vee f(i, l) > 0 \wedge l \neq Elec. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z}_{lb}(l, t) + \mathbf{p}_f(i, l, t) &\geq \delta_f(i, l) \mathbf{y}_{lb}(i, t) (1 - \%_{loss}(l)) \\
&\quad \forall i \in TECH \setminus STO, \forall l \in L \cap RES, \forall t \in T | f(i, l) > 0 \wedge l = Elec. \\
\mathbf{F}_t(i, t) &\leq \mathbf{y}_{lb}(i, t) \quad \forall i \in TECH \setminus STO, \forall t \in T
\end{aligned}$$

In Eqs. 34 Γ_{lb} is the protection parameter, \mathbf{z}_{lb} and \mathbf{p}_f are the dual variables, δ_f is the maximum worst-case deviation from the nominal value of f , calculated as in Eq. 35, in which δ_η is the maximum worst-case deviation from the nominal efficiencies (η) of energy conversion technologies.

$$\delta_f = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\delta_\eta}{\eta - \delta_\eta} = -f \frac{\delta_\eta}{\eta - \delta_\eta}, & \text{if } f < 0 \\ \delta_\eta = f \frac{\delta_\eta}{\eta}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

For the other layers, Eqs. 36 apply.

$$\sum_{l \in L | l \in EUT \text{ OF } EUC(euc)} \mathbf{LB} - \mathbf{z}_{lb}(l, t) \Gamma_{lb} - \sum_{i \in TECH \setminus STO} \mathbf{p}_f(i, euc, t) - \sum_{eui \in EUI \text{ OF } EUC(euc) s \in S} \sum \mathbf{p}_{dem}(eui, s, t) \geq 0 \quad \forall euc \in EUC, \forall t \in T \quad (36)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z}_{lb}(euc, t) + \mathbf{p}_{dem}(eui, s, t) &\geq \delta_{dem}(eui, s) \frac{\%_{lighting}(t)}{t_{op}(t)} \\
&\quad \forall euc \in EUC, \forall eui \in EUI \text{ OF } EUC(euc), \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T | eui = Lighting
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z}_{lb}(euc, t) + \mathbf{p}_{dem}(eui, s, t) &\geq \delta_{dem}(eui, s) \frac{\%_{sh}(t)}{t_{op}(t)} \\
&\quad \forall euc \in EUC, \forall eui \in EUI \text{ OF } EUC(euc), \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T | eui = Heat LowT SH
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z}_{lb}(euc, t) + \mathbf{p}_{dem}(eui, s, t) &\geq \frac{\delta_{dem}(eui, s)}{\sum_{t \in T} t_{op}(t)} \\
&\quad \forall euc \in EUC, \forall eui \in EUI \text{ OF } EUC(euc), \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T | eui \notin \{Lighting, Heat LowT SH\}
\end{aligned}$$

3 Data: uncertainty ranges

Table 6 reports the nominal values and ranges of variation of the considered uncertain parameters for robust optimization. Units as in Table 1. The data sources for the nominal values are reported in [1], Appendix A. The uncertainty ranges are defined with the methodology and data in [6].

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
i_{rate}	0.03215	0.0173	0.047
c_{op} (ELECTRICITY)	0.09006	0.04742	0.17104
c_{op} (GASOLINE)	0.08796	0.04631	0.16705
c_{op} (DIESEL)	0.08516	0.04484	0.16173
c_{op} (LFO)	0.06059	0.0319	0.11508
c_{op} (NG)	0.03482	0.01833	0.06613
c_{op} (WOOD)	0.0932	0.09045	0.09595
c_{op} (COAL)	0.03017	0.01588	0.05729
c_{op} (URANIUM)	0.00414	0.00218	0.00786
c_{inv} (NUCLEAR)	5174.8	4057.6	11346.7
c_{inv} (CCGT)	824.4	646.4	1030.5
c_{inv} (CCGT_CCS)	1273.3	768.6	1777.9
c_{inv} (COAL_US)	2687.6	2107.4	3359.4
c_{inv} (COAL_IGCC)	3466.2	2092.4	4840
c_{inv} (COAL_US_CCS)	4327.3	2612.2	6042.3
c_{inv} (COAL_IGCC_CCS)	6044.8	3649	8440.6
c_{inv} (PV)	1000	603.7	1396.3
c_{inv} (WIND)	1465.6	1149.2	1801.6
c_{inv} (HYDRO_DAM)	4828.4	3786	8393
c_{inv} (NEW_HYDRO_DAM)	3437.1	2695.1	5974.6
c_{inv} (HYDRO_RIVER)	5387.5	4224.4	6550.6
c_{inv} (NEW_HYDRO_RIVER)	5919.2	4641.3	7197.1
c_{inv} (GEOTHERMAL)	11464.1	6910.5	18580.3
c_{inv} (IND_COGEN_GAS)	1503.6	1179	1828.3
c_{inv} (IND_COGEN_WOOD)	1154.2	905	1403.4
c_{inv} (IND_COGEN_WASTE)	3126.7	2451.7	3801.7
c_{inv} (IND_BOILER_GAS)	62.9	49.3	76.5
c_{inv} (IND_BOILER_WOOD)	123	96.4	149.6
c_{inv} (IND_BOILER_OIL)	58.6	45.9	71.2
c_{inv} (IND_BOILER_COAL)	123	96.4	149.6
c_{inv} (IND_BOILER_WASTE)	123	96.4	149.6
c_{inv} (IND_DIRECT_ELEC)	354.9	278.3	431.5
c_{inv} (DHN_HP_ELEC)	368.2	288.7	447.7
c_{inv} (DHN_COGEN_GAS)	1339.7	1050.5	1628.9
c_{inv} (DHN_COGEN_WOOD)	1154.2	905	1403.4
c_{inv} (DHN_COGEN_WASTE)	3126.7	2451.7	3801.7
c_{inv} (DHN_BOILER_GAS)	62.9	49.3	76.5
c_{inv} (DHN_BOILER_WOOD)	123	96.4	149.6

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
c_{inv} (DHN_BOILER_OIL)	58.6	45.9	71.2
c_{inv} (DHN_DEEP_GEO)	1620.1	976.6	2625.8
c_{inv} (DEC_HP_ELEC)	525.5	412	638.9
c_{inv} (DEC_THHP_GAS)	337.1	264.3	409.9
c_{inv} (DEC_COGEN_GAS)	1503.6	1179	1828.3
c_{inv} (DEC_COGEN_OIL)	1394.2	1093.2	1695.2
c_{inv} (DEC_ADVCOGEN_GAS)	7734	4668.7	10799.3
c_{inv} (DEC_ADVCOGEN_H2)	7734	4668.7	10799.3
c_{inv} (DEC_BOILER_GAS)	169.3	132.8	205.8
c_{inv} (DEC_BOILER_WOOD)	493.8	387.2	600.5
c_{inv} (DEC_BOILER_OIL)	152.1	119.2	184.9
c_{inv} (DEC_SOLAR)	767.9	602.1	933.7
c_{inv} (DEC_DIRECT_ELEC)	42.69	33.47	51.91
c_{inv} (POWER2GAS)	0.41	0.25	0.58
c_{inv} (POWER2GAS.3)	3118.4	1882.5	4354.4
c_{inv} (EFFICIENCY)	1856	1126.8	2585.2
c_{inv} (DHN)	882	535.4	1228.5
c_{inv} (GRID)	61100	37093.7	85106.3
c_{inv} (H2_ELECTROLYSIS)	328.5	198.3	458.7
c_{inv} (H2_NG)	727.5	439.2	1015.8
c_{inv} (H2_BIOMASS)	2696.9	1628	3765.7
c_{inv} (GASIFICATION_SNG)	2930.1	1768.8	4091.4
c_{inv} (PYROLYSIS)	1435.5	866.5	2004.4
c_{maint} (NUCLEAR)	109.92	56.98	149.19
c_{maint} (CCGT)	21.07	10.92	28.6
c_{maint} (CCGT_CCS)	30.23	15.67	41.03
c_{maint} (COAL_US)	31.72	16.44	43.05
c_{maint} (COAL_IGCC)	52.27	27.1	70.94
c_{maint} (COAL_US_CCS)	67.58	35.03	91.72
c_{maint} (COAL_IGCC_CCS)	73.86	38.29	100.24
c_{maint} (PV)	15.88	8.23	21.55
c_{maint} (WIND)	22.9	11.87	31.08
c_{maint} (HYDRO_DAM)	24.14	12.51	32.76
c_{maint} (NEW_HYDRO_DAM)	2.89	1.5	3.92
c_{maint} (HYDRO_RIVER)	53.87	27.93	73.11
c_{maint} (NEW_HYDRO_RIVER)	76.28	39.54	103.53
c_{maint} (GEO_THERMAL)	465.04	241.07	631.16
c_{maint} (IND_COGEN_GAS)	98.9	51.27	134.23
c_{maint} (IND_COGEN_WOOD)	43.24	22.41	58.69
c_{maint} (IND_COGEN_WASTE)	118.88	61.63	161.35
c_{maint} (IND_BOILER_GAS)	1.26	0.65	1.71
c_{maint} (IND_BOILER_WOOD)	2.46	1.28	3.34
c_{maint} (IND_BOILER_OIL)	1.26	0.65	1.71
c_{maint} (IND_BOILER_COAL)	2.46	1.28	3.34
c_{maint} (IND_BOILER_WASTE)	2.46	1.28	3.34

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
c_{maint} (IND_DIRECT_ELEC)	1.61	0.83	2.19
c_{maint} (DHN_HP_ELEC)	12.81	6.64	17.39
c_{maint} (DHN_COGEN_GAS)	40.08	20.78	54.4
c_{maint} (DHN_COGEN_WOOD)	43.24	22.41	58.69
c_{maint} (DHN_COGEN_WASTE)	118.88	61.63	161.35
c_{maint} (DHN_BOILER_GAS)	1.26	0.65	1.71
c_{maint} (DHN_BOILER_WOOD)	2.46	1.28	3.34
c_{maint} (DHN_BOILER_OIL)	1.26	0.65	1.71
c_{maint} (DHN_DEEP_GEO)	60.12	31.17	81.6
c_{maint} (DEC_HP_ELEC)	22.48	11.65	30.51
c_{maint} (DEC_THHP_GAS)	10.11	5.24	13.72
c_{maint} (DEC_COGEN_GAS)	98.9	51.27	134.23
c_{maint} (DEC_COGEN_OIL)	87.53	45.37	118.8
c_{maint} (DEC_ADVCOGEN_GAS)	154.68	80.18	209.93
c_{maint} (DEC_ADVCOGEN_H2)	154.68	80.18	209.93
c_{maint} (DEC_BOILER_GAS)	5.08	2.63	6.89
c_{maint} (DEC_BOILER_WOOD)	17.28	8.96	23.45
c_{maint} (DEC_BOILER_OIL)	9.12	4.73	12.38
c_{maint} (DEC_SOLAR)	8.64	4.48	11.73
c_{maint} (DEC_DIRECT_ELEC)	0.19	0.1	0.26
c_{maint} (POWER2GAS_3)	155.92	80.83	211.62
c_{maint} (H2_ELECTROLYSIS)	32.85	17.03	44.58
c_{maint} (H2_NG)	68.81	35.67	93.39
c_{maint} (H2_BIOMASS)	208.99	108.34	283.64
c_{maint} (GASIFICATION_SNG)	149.44	77.47	202.82
c_{maint} (PYROLYSIS)	71.77	37.2	97.41
n (NUCLEAR)	60	44.1	75.9
n (CCGT)	25	18.4	31.6
n (CCGT_CCS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (COAL_US)	35	25.7	44.3
n (COAL_IGCC)	35	25.7	44.3
n (COAL_US_CCS)	35	25.7	44.3
n (COAL_IGCC_CCS)	35	25.7	44.3
n (PV)	25	18.4	31.6
n (WIND)	20	14.7	25.3
n (HYDRO_DAM)	40	29.4	50.6
n (NEW_HYDRO_DAM)	40	29.4	50.6
n (HYDRO_RIVER)	40	29.4	50.6
n (NEW_HYDRO_RIVER)	40	29.4	50.6
n (GEOTHERMAL)	30	22.1	37.9
n (IND_COGEN_GAS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (IND_COGEN_WOOD)	25	18.4	31.6
n (IND_COGEN_WASTE)	25	18.4	31.6
n (IND_BOILER_GAS)	17	12.5	21.5
n (IND_BOILER_WOOD)	17	12.5	21.5

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
n (IND_BOILER_OIL)	17	12.5	21.5
n (IND_BOILER_COAL)	17	12.5	21.5
n (IND_BOILER_WASTE)	17	12.5	21.5
n (IND_DIRECT_ELEC)	15	11	19
n (DHN_HP_ELEC)	25	18.4	31.6
n (DHN_COGEN_GAS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (DHN_COGEN_WOOD)	25	18.4	31.6
n (DHN_COGEN_WASTE)	25	18.4	31.6
n (DHN_BOILER_GAS)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DHN_BOILER_WOOD)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DHN_BOILER_OIL)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DHN_DEEP_GEO)	30	22.1	37.9
n (DEC_HP_ELEC)	18	13.2	22.8
n (DEC_THHP_GAS)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_COGEN_GAS)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_COGEN_OIL)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_ADVCOGEN_GAS)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_ADVCOGEN_H2)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_BOILER_GAS)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DEC_BOILER_WOOD)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DEC_BOILER_OIL)	17	12.5	21.5
n (DEC_SOLAR)	20	14.7	25.3
n (DEC_DIRECT_ELEC)	15	11	19
n (POWER2GAS_3)	25	18.4	31.6
n (DHN)	60	44.1	75.9
n (GRID)	80	58.8	101.2
n (H2_ELECTROLYSIS)	15	11	19
n (H2_NG)	25	18.4	31.6
n (H2_BIOMASS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (POWER2GAS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (PYROLYSIS)	25	18.4	31.6
n (POWER2GAS)	25	18.4	31.6
$c_{p,t}$ (group) (PV)	1.00	0.89	1.11
$c_{p,t}$ (group) (WIND)	1.00	0.89	1.11
$c_{p,t}$ (group) (HYDRO_DAM)	1.00	0.89	1.11
$c_{p,t}$ (group) (HYDRO_RIVER)	1.00	0.89	1.11
$c_{p,t}$ (group) (DEC_SOLAR)	1.00	0.89	1.11
d_{year} (ELECTRICITY,HOUSEHOLDS)	10848.1	10095.6	11317.5
d_{year} (ELECTRICITY,SERVICES)	15026.5	13916.6	15637.2
d_{year} (ELECTRICITY,INDUSTRY)	10443.5	9343.8	11064.9
d_{year} (LIGHTING,HOUSEHOLDS)	425.1	395.6	443.5
d_{year} (LIGHTING,SERVICES)	3805.2	3524.1	3959.8
d_{year} (LIGHTING,INDUSTRY)	1263.8	1130.7	1339.0
d_{year} (HEAT_HIGH_T,INDUSTRY)	19021.5	17018.5	20153.3
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_SH,HOUSEHOLDS)	29489.2	27443.5	30765.1

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_SH,SERVICES)	14524.8	13452.0	15115.1
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_SH,INDUSTRY)	4947.5	4426.5	5241.9
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_HW,HOUSEHOLDS)	7537.8	7014.9	7863.9
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_HW,SERVICES)	3256.0	3015.5	3388.3
d_{year} (HEAT_LOW_T_HW,INDUSTRY)	1281.8	1146.8	1358.1
d_{year} (MOBILITY_PASSENGER,TRANSPORTATION)	146049.3	141126.3	150972.3
d_{year} (MOBILITY_FREIGHT,TRANSPORTATION)	39966.7	38619.5	41313.9
f (NUCLEAR,URANIUM)	-2.7027	-2.8650	-2.5578
f (CCGT,NG)	-1.5873	-1.6826	-1.5022
f (CCGT_CCS,NG_CCS)	-1.7544	-1.8597	-1.6604
f (COAL_US,COAL)	-2.0408	-2.1633	-1.9314
f (COAL_IGCC,COAL)	-1.8519	-1.9631	-1.7526
f (COAL_US_CCS,COAL_CCS)	-2.3810	-2.5239	-2.2534
f (COAL_IGCC_CCS,COAL_CCS)	-2.0833	-2.2084	-1.9716
f (IND_COGEN_GAS,ELECTRICITY)	0.9565	0.9023	1.0107
f (IND_COGEN_WOOD,ELECTRICITY)	0.3396	0.3204	0.3588
f (IND_COGEN_WASTE,ELECTRICITY)	0.4444	0.4192	0.4696
f (IND_BOILER_GAS,NG)	-1.0785	-1.1432	-1.0207
f (IND_BOILER_WOOD,WOOD)	-1.1568	-1.2262	-1.0948
f (IND_BOILER_OIL,LFO)	-1.1461	-1.2149	-1.0847
f (IND_BOILER_COAL,COAL)	-1.2195	-1.2927	-1.1541
f (IND_BOILER_WASTE,WASTE)	-1.2195	-1.2927	-1.1541
f (IND_DIRECT_ELEC,ELECTRICITY)	-1.0000	-1.0600	-1.0000
f (DHN_HP_ELEC,ELECTRICITY)	-0.2500	-0.2650	-0.2366
f (DHN_COGEN_GAS,ELECTRICITY)	1.2500	1.1792	1.3208
f (DHN_COGEN_WOOD,ELECTRICITY)	0.3396	0.3204	0.3588
f (DHN_COGEN_WASTE,ELECTRICITY)	0.4444	0.3530	0.5358
f (DHN_BOILER_GAS,NG)	-1.0785	-1.1432	-1.0207
f (DHN_BOILER_WOOD,WOOD)	-1.1568	-1.2262	-1.0948
f (DHN_BOILER_OIL,LFO)	-1.1461	-1.2149	-1.0847
f (DEC_HP_ELEC,ELECTRICITY)	-0.3333	-0.3533	-0.3154
f (DEC_THHP_GAS,NG)	-0.6667	-0.7067	-0.6310
f (DEC_COGEN_GAS,ELECTRICITY)	0.9565	0.9023	1.0107
f (DEC_COGEN_OIL,ELECTRICITY)	0.9070	0.8556	0.9584
f (DEC_ADVCOGEN_GAS,ELECTRICITY)	2.6364	2.0884	3.1844
f (DEC_ADVCOGEN_H2,ELECTRICITY)	2.6364	2.0884	3.1844
f (DEC_BOILER_GAS,NG)	-1.1111	-1.1778	-1.0515
f (DEC_BOILER_WOOD,WOOD)	-1.1765	-1.2471	-1.1134
f (DEC_BOILER_OIL,LFO)	-1.1765	-1.2471	-1.1134
f (DEC_DIRECT_ELEC,ELECTRICITY)	-1.0000	-1.0600	-1.0000
f (TRAMWAY_TROLLEY,ELECTRICITY)	-0.1653	-0.1752	-0.1564
f (BUS_COACH_DIESEL,DIESEL)	-0.2655	-0.2814	-0.2513
f (BUS_COACH_HYDIESEL,DIESEL)	-0.1828	-0.2308	-0.1513
f (BUS_COACH_CNG_STOICH,NG)	-0.3062	-0.3246	-0.2898
f (BUS_COACH_FC_HYBRIDH2,H2)	-0.2255	-0.2847	-0.1867

Table 6: Parameters: nominal values and upper/lower bounds

Parameter name	Nominal	Min	Max
<i>f</i> (TRAIN_PUB,ELECTRICITY)	-0.0917	-0.0972	-0.0868
<i>f</i> (CAR_GASOLINE,GASOLINE)	-0.4297	-0.5410	-0.3564
<i>f</i> (CAR_DIESEL,DIESEL)	-0.3868	-0.4870	-0.3208
<i>f</i> (CAR_NG,NG)	-0.4826	-0.6076	-0.4002
<i>f</i> (CAR_HEV,GASOLINE)	-0.2471	-0.3465	-0.1920
<i>f</i> (CAR_PHEV,GASOLINE)	-0.1760	-0.2468	-0.1368
<i>f</i> (CAR_BEV,ELECTRICITY)	-0.1066	-0.1495	-0.0828
<i>f</i> (CAR_FUEL_CELL,H2)	-0.1794	-0.2516	-0.1394
<i>f</i> (TRAIN_FREIGHT,ELECTRICITY)	-0.0683	-0.0724	-0.0646
<i>f</i> (TRUCK,DIESEL)	-0.5126	-0.5434	-0.4851
<i>f</i> (POWER2GAS_1,LNG)	0.7920	0.7471	0.8369
<i>f</i> (H2_ELECTROLYSIS,ELECTRICITY)	-1.1765	-1.2471	-1.1134
<i>f</i> (H2_NG,NG)	-1.3646	-1.4465	-1.2915
<i>f</i> (H2_BIOMASS,WOOD)	-2.3121	-2.4509	-2.1882

4 Data: installed capacity and electricity demand in Europe

The detailed data of installed capacity and demand used in Figure 1 and Table 1 of the paper are reported together with their sources in the attachment `moret_overcapacity_2019_ESI.xlsx`, where we additionally report the data for all other ENTSO-E countries.

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